

Milestone: MS11 - Inventory & summary of updated TRE Provider capabilities

Lead Participant: CSC

Author: WP11

Due: 30.08.2025

Date of Completion: 29.08.2025

Means of Verification

[Updated TRE Inventory](#)

[Summary of updated TRE Provider capabilities](#)

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No

Project participants & others

CSC (EUDAT), BSC, HEALTH-RI, SIGMA2, DeIC, BIP4DAB, UTARTU, PNED, UL, IT4I@VSB, VIB, Sciansano, THL, GRNET, UNIBI, UU

Next action steps

Creating a document outlining updates and revisions needed for final inventory version in 2026

Promoting the MS11 inventory and summary amongst project partners and stakeholders